

ASSESSMENT OF STATE OF DISPERSION FOR EPOXY/CNT NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The relation between the state of dispersion and the cure kinetics behavior of thermosetting resin was investigated by using the differential scanning calorimeter (DSC). A method to assess the overall state of dispersion has been proposed from the change in cure kinetics. Moreover, tensile tests were conducted for various dispersion states.

Keywords : nano particle, carbon nanotube, differential scanning calorimeter, degree of dispersion,

INTRODUCTION

In polymeric composite system, nano-particles have a great potential as fillers because of their extremely high surface to volume ratio [1]. In case of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) reinforced composite materials, the mechanical properties were found to vary widely, from no improvement [2] to moderate increase. Even though the mechanical properties of composites that contain CNTs have shown improvement, the increases of mechanical properties were not of the same degree [4-6]. There was a report that the Young's modulus was improved by 100% by the addition of 1wt% of CNTs into epoxy matrix [4]. However, in another study [5], the improvement was not substantial for the same amount of CNTs. The variation in the extent of improvement may be due to factors such as the state of dispersion and orientation of CNT particles as well as the interface between the particles and the matrix [6]. Of these, dispersion may play an important role as homogeneous dispersion guarantees uniform load-sharing by the reinforcing particles [8].

Assessment of degree of dispersion generally has been achieved by optical methods such as optical microscope, SEM, or TEM [6,7]. These direct observation methods make it possible to observe individual particles and assess the degree of dispersion easily. However, rather complex processes should be carried out for these methods and the images obtained from these methods are only for a small part of the cross-section. In Figure 1, limitations of direct observation methods are illustrated. All three cases in Figure 1 have identical number of particles with different configurations. Direct

observation methods can distinguish (a) and (b), but cannot tell the difference between (b) and (c) depending on the location of observation.

Figure 1 States of nano-particle dispersion:(a) aggregated and inhomogeneous dispersion, (b) non-aggregated and inhomogeneous, and (c) non-aggregated and homogenous.

Meanwhile, it has been observed that the cure kinetics of the resin can change when nano-particles are added. For instance, the use of different solvents to disperse CNTs resulted in different degrees of change in the cure kinetics of epoxy resin even after the solvents are completely removed [7]. From these researches, it may be speculated that nano-size particles can affect the cure kinetics by acting as obstacles to the chemical reaction. The effect of nano-particles may be related to the number of nano-particles that are dispersed in the thermosetting resin. In other words, the relationship between the cure kinetics and the number of well-dispersed nano-particles can lead to a way of assessing the state of dispersion [8].

In this study, the change in cure kinetics of thermosetting resin in the presence of CNTs was observed and from the value of total heat of reaction of the sample, and assessment of dispersion was performed. In addition, the change in mechanical properties of composite was investigated when the state of CNT dispersion in the sample was varied.

EXPERIMENT DETAILS

Materials

Multi-walled CNTs (by Hanhwa Nanotech in Korea) were used as nano-filler and the chemical treatment of CNTs was not performed to factor out any effect other than dispersion. The diameters of carbon nanotubes ranged from 10 to 15 nm and the length of carbon nanotubes were from 10 to 20 μm . A bisphenol-A type epoxy resin (YD114 by Kukdo Chemical in Korea) was used with KBH1089 (by Kukdo Chemical in Korea) as a curing agent.

Dispersion Process

CNTs were entangled with each other. In order to facilitate dispersion, epoxy resin was diluted using a solvent. First, epoxy resin was dissolved in acetone and CNTs were dispersed in the solution using the conical ultrasonicator (CV 505 power supply and CV 33 convertor from Sonics & Materials, Inc.). In order to obtain different states of dispersion, the duration of ultrasonication was varied from 12 to 24 hours. Here, ultrasonic energy was applied for one second for every three seconds. The second step was the removal of the solvent in a low-power ultrasonic bath (SD-D300H from SeongDong in Korea) for 48 hours. The residual solvent was further eliminated in a vacuum oven at 80°C for four hours. Hardener was added to the mixture right before the DSC measurement.

Cure Kinetics

According to the previous work [8], an increase in the CNT concentration resulted in a smaller heat of reaction. This decrease may be attributed to individual CNTs that block the cross-linking reaction. Aggregated CNTs are much less efficient in blocking chemical reactions and have minimal effect on the value of the total heat of reaction. Therefore, the decrease in the total heat of reaction through ideal dispersion can be obtained by ignoring the mass of aggregated CNTs. Following this assumption, the “degree of dispersion” that indicated how well the particles are dispersed may be defined as the ratio of the decrease in the total heat of reaction of the sample to that of the decrease in the ideal value as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 The total heat of reaction for ideal dispersion concentrations obtained by subtracting the aggregated mass of CNT. (Reproduced from [8])

The change in cure kinetics of epoxy resin containing CNT particles was investigated experimentally using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) (Q1000, TA

Instruments) to measure the total heat of reaction. DSC measurements were done by raising the sample temperature at a rate of 10°C/min. The sample size ranged from 3mg to 5mg. Three samples were prepared from each specimen with the same dispersion condition. Scans were performed for these three samples to obtain average values.

Mechanical Tests

In order to investigate the effects of dispersion, tensile tests were conducted. Specimens of tensile tests were prepared according to the ASTM D 638 type 1 standard.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Assessment of Dispersion

As stated above, the degree of dispersion in CNT-epoxy resin is defined as the ratio between the measured and the ideal values of the decrease in the total heat of reaction. In Figure 2, values of total heat of reaction for ideally dispersed mixture for different CNT concentrations (data listed in Table 1) are plotted. The fitted curve to these data points can be considered as the decrease in the total heat of reaction for ideally dispersed mixtures and may serve as a reference to determine the state of dispersion in mixtures.

Table 1 The ideal values of the total heat of reactions at several CNT concentration

CNT Concentration (wt%)	Total heat of reaction (J/g)
0.1	267.0
0.2	248.4
0.3	231.3

Three samples with the same concentration (0.3wt%) but with different dispersion states were prepared by varying the ultrasonication time. The values of total heat of reaction of samples were 281.3, 287.1 and 292.2 J/g. Since the ideal value of the total heat of reaction at 0.3wt% was 231.3 J/g, the degree of dispersion of each sample were estimated to be 0.495, 0.437, and 0.385, respectively. The degrees of dispersion of the samples are given in Table 2.

According to these results we can see that the longer sonication time can result in better dispersion states of samples. It is noted that extended exposure to high ultrasonic energy may introduce defects in the CNTs [10] and thus adversely affect the mechanical properties.

Table 2 Degree of dispersion for various concentrations and ultrasonication time

CNT concentration	Sample No.	Ultrasonication time (hr)	Degree of dispersion ($\Delta H_{\text{sample}} / \Delta H_{\text{ideal}}$)
0.1wt%	1	24	0.904
	2	18	0.700
	3	12	0.322
0.2wt%	1	24	0.854
	2	18	0.567
	3	12	0.364
0.3wt%	1	24	0.495
	2	18	0.437
	3	12	0.385

Mechanical Properties

The tensile modulus of pure epoxy resin was measured to be 3.03GPa. Since the dispersion state of the sample is related to the load transfer efficiency, we assumed that better dispersion of CNT leads to a higher increase in the mechanical properties. It was found that the increase in the degree of dispersion led to an increase in the Young's modulus (Figures 3a-3c) for samples with the same CNT concentrations. For samples with different CNT concentrations, the absolute amount of well-dispersed particles may be a key factor in the extent of increase in mechanical properties. The amount of well dispersed particles may be estimated by multiplying the CNT concentration with the degree of dispersion. In Figure 3d, the normalized Young's modulus for different amounts of well dispersed particles is plotted. As can be seen, depending on the state of dispersion, samples with lower CNT concentration exhibited larger modulus than samples with higher concentration. Aggregated particles usually do not have load bearing capability of individual particles. Rather, sometimes they may act as defects. At higher concentration, amount of aggregated particles and thus the number of defects may increase (see Figure 4). Therefore, the state of dispersion may become more crucial to the strengthening effect of CNT particles as the concentration becomes larger.

Figure 3 Normalized Young's modulus for different degrees of dispersion and the amount of well-dispersed particles: (a) CNT concentration 0.1wt%, (b) 0.2wt%, (c) 0.3wt%, and (d) normalized Young's modulus versus amounts of well-dispersed particles.

Figure 4 Normalized Young's modulus of composite for the amount of aggregated particles

CONCLUSIONS

Using the results from DSC analysis, the dispersion state of a sample could be assessed qualitatively. For different degrees of dispersion, the change in mechanical properties of composite was investigated. In general, as the dispersion value of a sample became higher, Young's modulus was increased. However, the key to the extent of improvement seemed to be the number of well dispersed particles, not the absolute amount of CNTs.

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